

Driving Customer Satisfaction and Stimulating Repurchase Intention: Insights from Palestinian Digital Retailers

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ABSTRACT

Recently, driven by the spread of advanced digital platforms and social media, many traditional brick-and-mortar retailers have ventured into the online marketplace to expand their sales channels. This research explores the crucial factors shaping customer satisfaction in local online retail. Furthermore, it examines how this level of satisfaction influences customers' intentions to repurchase within the online sales channel. This study collected primary data by administering questionnaires to 410 customers. The research employs both Maximum Likelihood and Bayesian Structural Equation Modeling to measure the causal pathways of the outlined in the research model. The study's findings indicate that information availability, perceived price, perceived quality, customer support, time-saving, and delivery services all have a positive and significant influence on customer satisfaction, with statistical significance at $p < .05$. Together, these exogenous variables account for 63% of the variation in customer satisfaction. Furthermore, the results demonstrate that customer satisfaction plays a significant and positive role in influencing customer repurchase intention in the online sales channel, explaining a substantial 74% of the variance in repurchase intention. The study's findings highlight the importance for local retailers to acknowledge and prioritize the factors contributing to customer satisfaction. To achieve this, retailers must ensure that all product information, images, and terms and conditions are not only accurate but also clear and comprehensive. This way, customers have a precise understanding of what products they are purchasing, the quantity, and the details of the delivery process, including when and where they can expect to receive their orders.

Keywords: Customer Satisfaction, Online Order, Online Sales Channel, Retailer Viability, /9*-

INTRODUCTION

Online local retail falls under the Offline-to-Online (O2O) channel. Retailers with physical stores offer their products to local online customers who live within 50 kilometers of the physical store (Vasefi, 2019). This strategy allows customers the convenience of either driving to the store for curbside pickup or receiving swift local delivery services directly from the store. Online local shopping is becoming increasingly popular among consumers due to the expanding capabilities of smartphones (Bourg *et al.*, 2021), the development of mobile applications (Khrais and Alghamdi, 2021), and the widespread use of social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram (Xi *et al.*, 2020). These technological advancements have greatly facilitated and enriched the online shopping experience, contributing to the rising trend in digital local retail (Moon *et al.*, 2021).

While the online local retail shopping experience may share similarities with the global online experience for customers, distinct characteristics set them apart (Barton, 2023, Pace, 2021, Brown, 2023). In the online local retail, several unique factors come into play. For instance, customers have high expectations regarding the prompt delivery of their purchases, often anticipating receipt within hours or days. Additionally, customers have multiple avenues for making online orders, including through the local retailer's social media profiles, their dedicated local business website, and even via phone calls (Brown, 2023). Moreover, certain types of purchases, like groceries, tend to occur regularly, with customers ordering them weekly or bimonthly (He *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, customers are less sensitive to security and trust factors as they can easily reach the physical store and return the purchased products—an option that is not as readily available on global online sites (Park *et al.*, 2012). Given these distinctions, the drivers of customer satisfaction in online local retail are likely different from those in the global online shopping arena.

Customer satisfaction is a crucial distinguishing factor for both offline and online businesses, aiding them in attracting and retaining customers within competitive business environments (Hult *et al.*, 2019)□. Satisfied customers are more likely to repeat purchases and even become advocates who recommend the retailer to others. Consequently, it becomes imperative for retailers to identify and assess the antecedents that drive customer satisfaction in online local retail channels. Customer satisfaction and retention contribute significantly to the retailer's overall gains in the market, including profit and growth (Bhattacharya *et al.*, 2020).

Studies covering customer satisfaction in the retail and grocery market are abundant. Many researchers investigated the factors influencing customer satisfaction in physical brick-and-mortar stores (Theodoridis and Chatzipanagiotou, 2009, Nair, 2018, Konuk, 2019, Slack and Singh, 2020). Simultaneously, the satisfaction of online shoppers in the global e-commerce arena, such as Amazon and Alibaba, has been extensively examined by scholars such as Sreeram *et al.* (2017), (Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Wahab and Khong, 2019, Gao, 2021, Javed and Wu, 2020). Yet, despite this extensive research landscape, customer satisfaction within the online local market remains relatively unexplored. Previous studies have primarily focused on service delivery and mobile food applications in this context, as demonstrated by the investigations of Suhartanto *et al.* (2019), Bonny, (2019), Alalwan, (2020), Tandon *et al.*, (2020). However, these studies have not explored the drivers of customer satisfaction within the broader online local retail sector, including categories such as groceries, home appliances, and more.

Moreover, these studies have not assessed the impact of customer satisfaction on the intention to repurchase within the online local sales channel. Repurchase intention is a direct outcome of customer satisfaction (Fang *et al.*, 2011, Lim *et al.*, 2018). Customers are more inclined to return for future transactions when pleased with their previous purchases and overall experience. Repetitive buying from the same retailer generates consistent revenue and reduces acquisition costs associated with attracting new customers. It can also lead to cross-selling and upselling opportunities, where satisfied customers may explore and purchase additional products or services from the retailer (Keller and Kotler, 2015). Retailers that effectively maintain high levels of customer satisfaction and repurchase intention are more likely to succeed in a competitive marketplace and establish a long-term customer base (Ibzan *et al.*, 2016).

Customer satisfaction in local online retail is influenced by unique factors such as cultural, economic, and social contexts, which differ significantly from global retail settings. Further, local retailers' adoption of technology also varies, affecting customer satisfaction distinctly. Addressing these gaps will provide crucial insights into improving

strategies for enhancing customer satisfaction in local online retail environments. Given these research gaps, there is a compelling need to investigate this area further to gain a comprehensive understanding of its dynamics and implications.

This empirical study serves two primary objectives. Firstly, it aims to identify and measure the key factors that significantly influence customer satisfaction within the online local retail channel. Secondly, it seeks to explore the impact of customer satisfaction on customer repurchase intentions in the context of the online local retail channel. Collectively, these objectives contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play within this specific retail landscape.

This research carries significant practical implications that benefit retailers, consumers, and marketers. For instance, through understanding specific drivers of customer satisfaction in the online local retailers can innovate more effectively when they understand what truly satisfies their customers. This could lead to the development of new products and services specifically designed to meet the unique needs of local markets. For example, innovations in logistics and delivery services that satisfy specifically to local preferences for speed and convenience could emerge as a direct result of this research.

For marketers, detailed understanding into the drivers of customer satisfaction in the local online retail sector can inform more effective marketing strategies. These strategies can be linked to the unique characteristics of the local market, allowing for more precise targeting and segmentation.

For customers, understanding and enhancing customer satisfaction in the online local retail sector offers numerous benefits. Firstly, it leads to a more personalized and enjoyable shopping experience as retailers can tailor their services and products to meet customer expectations more effectively. Additionally, this focus on customer satisfaction often results in improved product quality and customer service. Innovations in logistics and delivery, driven by customer feedback, further increase convenience by ensuring faster and more reliable delivery services. Customers also benefit from increased trust and security in their transactions, knowing they have easy access to physical stores if issues arise. Lastly, supporting local online retailers who support to community needs also helps strengthen the local economy, leading to broader economic stability and job creation within the community.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 provides a comprehensive review of the relevant literature, covering customer satisfaction drivers and repurchase intention. Section 3 explores the conceptual framework supporting the study. Section 4 presents the empirical model, while Section 5 explains the research methodology. The findings of the study analysis are discussed in Section 6. Section 7 is dedicated to concluding and outlining practical implications and future directions for research in this domain.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The core premise of this paper is that customer satisfaction is a critical measure of success for online retailers. Satisfied customers are more driven to make repeat purchases. Retailers that effectively satisfy their customers not only secure opportunities for recurring sales but also strengthen their potential for increased revenue and long-term growth in the market.

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN ONLINE RETAIL CHANNEL

Seminal work on customer satisfaction encompasses key theoretical models. The Disconfirmation of Expectations Model suggests that customer satisfaction is determined by the difference between customers' expectations and experience (Westbrook and Oliver, 1981). If the customers' experience exceeds their expectations, they will be satisfied. They will be dissatisfied if their experience falls short of their expectations (Swan and Trawick, 1981, Anderson *et al.*, 1994). Furthermore, the Perceived Performance Model suggests that customer satisfaction derives from the customer's evaluation of the retailer's performance across several critical dimensions, including but not limited to product quality, availability, information, pricing, website usability, checkout process, delivery, and customer service (Cronin Jr and Taylor, 1992).

Previous research on customer satisfaction in online retail has identified several key factors influencing customer satisfaction. Both Wahab and Khong (2019), Vasefi, (2019) highlighted the significant role of retailer services—such as online ordering, personalization, and responsive customer support—in driving customer satisfaction. Complementing these findings, Pham and Ahammad (2017) emphasized the importance of order fulfillment, easy returns, and prompt responses in enhancing the online shopping experience. This satisfaction, in turn, has implications for repurchase intentions and positive referrals.

The quality and presentation of information provided by online sales channels are critical determinants of customer satisfaction. For instance, research conducted by Pham and Ahammad (2017), Tandon *et al.*, (2018), Sreeram *et al.*, (2017), Bonny, (2019), collectively indicate that clear, accessible, and comprehensive information enhances consumer trust and reduces uncertainty, thereby improving the overall shopping experience. Further emphasizing this point, Vasić *et al.* (2019) conducted a focused study on the online market of Serbia and discovered a positive correlation between the availability and quality of product information—including price and specifications—and consumer satisfaction. This research highlights the critical role of not only making information available but also ensuring its accuracy and completeness.

Online retail shopping offers customers convenience, hassle reduction, and time savings, which are strong incentives for choosing online over offline shopping (Sreeram *et al.*, 2017, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Gao, 2021, Alalwan, 2020). This convenience factor is particularly noticeable in avoiding in-store traffic, waiting lines, and cashiers. Research by Brand *et al.* (2020) highlighted that grocery shoppers prioritize shopping convenience, especially when faced with time pressures and busy schedules. These findings align with the previous studies emphasizing that shopping convenience and time-saving are significant determinants of online shopping behavior.

The comparison of prices, discounts, product quality, and potential cost savings between online and offline shopping is a common practice among customers (Suhartanto *et al.*, 2019, Rahman and Yu, 2019, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Brand *et al.*, 2020, Alalwan, 2020). In the fast-food service industry, Zhong and Moon (2020) found that perceived price significantly influences customer satisfaction, loyalty, and overall restaurant quality assessment. Customers' judgment of a restaurant's quality can be substantially shaped by the perceived price, emphasizing the importance of pricing strategies in online and offline shopping. Price and product quality have emerged as core predictors of customer satisfaction, as customers evaluate overall cost savings while considering the quality of products when shopping online compared to traditional offline methods (Cebollada *et al.*, 2019).

Ultimately, customer satisfaction in online retail extends beyond the immediate transaction to impact retailer continuity and performance. Retailers who successfully satisfy their customers gain the opportunity for repeat sales and enhance their potential for additional revenue and long-term viability in the market. This body of research underscores the importance of customer satisfaction and its subsequent effects on the success and longevity of online local retailers in today's competitive landscape, particularly regarding customer repurchase intention.

REPURCHASE INTENTION IN ONLINE RETAIL CHANNEL

Customer repurchase intention is the likelihood that a customer will repeat purchases from an online retailer (Wen *et al.*, 2011). Seminal work on online retail develops several theoretical models that explain the factors influencing customer repurchase intention (Chen, 2012). Reinartz *et al.* (2005) emphasized the importance of customer retention compared to customer acquisition. Their work explained the significant costs of acquiring new customers and the benefits of nurturing existing customer relationships. In online retail, understanding the factors that drive repurchase intention is essential for retaining customers and ensuring long-term profitability.

Barnes and Vidgen (2002) introduced the e-commerce quality model and emphasized that the quality of the online shopping experience, including website usability, product information, and overall service, influences customer behavior, including repurchase intentions. This multidimensional perspective provides insights into the various aspects of online retail that affect customer repurchase decisions. Oliver (2014) offered a behavioral perspective on consumer satisfaction, highlighting the role of cognitive evaluations and affective responses in shaping customer satisfaction. His work underscores the significance of understanding how customers perceive their online shopping

experiences and how these perceptions influence their likelihood of repurchasing from an online retailer. Zeithaml *et al.* (1996) explored the behavioral consequences of service quality in traditional retail settings. While their study was conducted before the widespread expansion of online retail, the fundamental principles of service quality and its impact on customer behavior remain relevant. Understanding how service quality translates into online customer repurchase intentions is essential for online retailers.

Measuring repurchase intention and customer satisfaction in the local retail sector is essential, particularly in the modern retail landscape where online and global competitors compete for consumers' attention. While a wealth of literature addresses these metrics in various retail contexts, the focus on the local retail sector remains notably understated. The significance of this study lies in its potential to bridge this gap and offer analyses tailored explicitly to local retailers, covering grocery stores, home appliance shops, clothing boutiques, and more.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL

This research assesses the causal-effect relationship by studying, in the first round, the links between the drivers of customer satisfaction as exogenous variables and customer satisfaction, along with repurchase intention, as endogenous variables. In the second round, the model assesses the impact of customer satisfaction and its drivers as exogenous variables on repurchase intention as an endogenous variable. Hence, the drivers of customer satisfaction, directly and indirectly, affect the intention to repurchase.

The dimensions of the conceptual framework based on the related literature are the following:

INFORMATION AVAILABILITY:

Product information holds significant importance in local online sales channels, as customers make their purchases online or via phone without the opportunity to interact physically with the products (Kashyap and Kumar, 2019). Product information includes descriptions, images, manufacturer or retailer-provided prices, discounts, and quality data. Given consumers' feelings toward comprehensive and trustworthy information, the availability of such information positively influences customer satisfaction (Pham and Ahammad, 2017, Tandon *et al.*, 2018, Sreeram *et al.*, 2017, Bonny, 2019, Vasić *et al.*, 2019) and repurchase intention (Miao *et al.*, 2022).

Based on this discussion and the results of previous studies, the research suggests the following two hypotheses

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- H0-1: There is a positive relationship between information availability and customer satisfaction in the online local retail channel**

- H0-2: There is a positive relationship between information availability and customer repurchase intention in the online local retail channel**

PERCEIVED QUALITY

The importance of product and service quality in ensuring retailer profitability and long-term sustainability has been widely acknowledged (Lim *et al.*, 2009). Perceived product quality, in particular, relates to a consumer's assessment of a product's overall excellence, including its features and characteristics that meet specified needs (Chen and Dubinsky, 2003). Customers may also gauge quality by considering the extent to which online local retailers offer prompt shipping and secure product delivery. Previous studies have demonstrated a positive and significant impact of product quality on customer satisfaction (Suhartanto *et al.*, 2019, Rahman and Yu, 2019, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Brand *et al.*, 2020, Alalwan, 2020), and both have influence on repurchase intention. (Patterson, 1993, Mahendrayanti and Wardana, 2021, Izzudin and Novandari, 2018).

- H0-3: There is a positive relationship between perceived quality and customer satisfaction in the online local retail channel**

- H0-4: There is a positive relationship between perceived quality and customer repurchase intention in the online local retail channel**

PERCEIVED PRICE

Perceived price holds a principal position in customer satisfaction, considering customers trade their valuable financial resources for the products and services retailers offer (Išoraitė, 2016). In addition to providing competitive prices, retailers must align their pricing strategies with the quality and quantity of the products and services provided to ensure customer satisfaction. Offering a lower price in the online sales channel compared to physical stores can increase customer satisfaction, particularly when customers believe they are receiving excellent value for their money. Previous research has consistently shown that price positively and significantly impacts customer satisfaction (Zhong and Moon, 2020, Jiang and Rosenbloom, 2005, Kartikasari and Albari, 2019). Based on the earlier studies, this study hypothesizes the following

- H0-5: There is a positive relationship between perceived price and customer satisfaction in the online local retail channel**

TIME-SAVING

Time and effort savings are noticeable incentives for online shoppers, as they can avoid travel time, parking hassles, and in-store crowds associated with physical stores (Vasić *et al.*, 2019). Time is a valuable resource that consumers invest when shopping, whether through online platforms or in brick-and-mortar establishments. When online shopping offers convenience and saves customers time compared to traditional brick-and-mortar shopping, it enhances customer satisfaction. Extensive research has established a statistically positive significant relationship between time-saving and perceived convenience, particularly in online grocery shopping (Sreeram *et al.*, 2017, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Gao, 2021, Alalwan, 2020, Brand *et al.*, 2020). Consequently, time positively correlates with customer satisfaction in online local retail.

- H0-6: There is a positive relationship between time-saving and customer satisfaction in the online local retail channel**

DELIVERY SERVICE

Product delivery service entails the customer receiving the ordered product in good condition, with quantity and quality matching their online order, and all within the specified delivery time, cost, and location (Patterson, 1993). Customers hold the expectation of dependable, secure, and punctual delivery services. Dissatisfaction arises when there are delays in delivery, discrepancies in product quality compared to the order, and low delivery service quality (Rajendran *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, delivery service establishes a positive relationship with customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in online local retail (Uzir *et al.*, 2021, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Cha and Shin, 2021, Roy Dholakia and Zhao, 2010).

H0-7: There is a positive relationship between delivery service and customer satisfaction in the online local retail channel

H0-8: There is a positive relationship between delivery service and customer repurchase intention in the online local retail channel

CUSTOMER SUPPORT

Customer support shapes customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions within the online local retail channel. In the digital scheme, customers often require assistance, guidance, or resolution to various issues that may arise during their shopping experience (Froehle, 2006). A responsive and efficient customer support system promptly meets customer needs. Whether addressing product inquiries, resolving order discrepancies, or assisting with returns and refunds, accessible and helpful customer support raises a sense of trust and reliability among customers. When customers perceive that their concerns are being addressed and resolved effectively, they are more likely to feel satisfied with their overall shopping experience (Yoon, 2010). This satisfaction, in turn, significantly influences their intention to repurchase from the same retailer (Cahyati and Seminari, 2020).

H0-9: There is a positive relationship between customer support and customer satisfaction in the online local retail channel

H0-10: There is a positive relationship between customer support and customer repurchase intention in the online local retail channel

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Customer satisfaction is vital for repurchase intention, reflecting the customer's pleasure with their shopping experience. In online local retail, customer satisfaction includes various dimensions, including the quality of products, the convenience of the shopping process, the efficiency of delivery services, and the responsiveness of customer support. When customers are pleased with these aspects, they are more motivated to express their intention to repurchase from the same retailer (Choi *et al.* 2019, Hult *et al.*, 2019, Tandon *et al.*, 2020, Dai and Lee, 2018). This is particularly crucial in the competitive landscape of online local retail, where numerous options are just a click away. Satisfied customers not only return for future purchases but also become advocates, sharing their positive experiences and driving word-of-mouth referrals (Ahn *et al.*, 2004, Guo *et al.*, 2012, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Choi *et al.*, 2019).

Repurchase intention reflects the customer's commitment to continue business with a specific online local retailer. Customers' satisfaction levels increase when they have positive shopping experiences, including factors like easy navigation, product quality, timely delivery, and responsive customer support. This heightened satisfaction, in turn, encourages customers to return for future purchases (Lin and Lekhawipat, 2014). It is a mutually reinforcing cycle where satisfied customers are more likely to become repeat customers, contributing not only to a retailer's short-term revenue but also to its long-term viability and growth in the competitive online local retail landscape.

H0-11: There is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and customer repurchase intention in the online local retail channel

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted in two main phases to identify and quantify customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions within the local retail channel. Initially, interviews were held with marketing experts to validate the exploratory variables associated with customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. Following this, primary data was gathered through customer surveys administered in the last quarter of 2023.

DATA COLLECTION

Primary data collection for this study was conducted through a survey of customers using the online retail channel. The survey questionnaire included a cover letter, followed by measurement items designed to assess customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions within this online retail context. The selection of measurement items was informed by a comprehensive review of the relevant literature, which is detailed in “Appendix 1”. The questionnaire was designed in English and Arabic to ensure clarity and accessibility for respondents.

The assessment of customer satisfaction within the context of online local shopping was structured through five selected survey items. Each item was designed to capture a different dimension of the customer’s satisfaction (Ahn *et al.*, 2004, Guo *et al.*, 2012, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Choi *et al.*, 2019). These dimensions range from emotional engagement (“Online local shopping makes the purchasing process interesting”) to behavioral intentions (“Would recommend online local shopping to other consumers”). Additional aspects explored through the survey included customers’ enjoyment of their shopping experience, their satisfaction with local retailers offering online options, and their overall evaluation of the quality of online local shopping.

In parallel, the concept of repurchase intention was measured through three targeted survey items, each focusing on the likelihood of future engagements with the same online local retailer Lin and Lekhawipat (2014). These items explored whether participants anticipate making future purchases (“Anticipate repurchasing from this online local retailer”), their probability of returning as customers (“Likely to repurchase from the same online local retailer”), and their expectations regarding continued patronage (“Expect to repurchase from the same online local retailer”). This measure aimed to measure the long-term repurchase intentions of the customers, thereby offering valuable predictors of ongoing business success and customer retention strategies for online local retailers.

The questionnaire utilized a five-point Likert scale, ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree,” allowing respondents to express their level of agreement with the provided statements. Data collection was conducted through an online questionnaire, which enhanced the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of distributing the survey (de Oña *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, using an online method, rather than a traditional paper-based approach, strategically targeted customers who are regular Internet and smartphone users. This alignment with the current and potential user base of the online local retail channel ensured that the responses were directly relevant to the digital commerce environment and online shopping.

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2}}{1 + \left(\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2 N} \right)} \quad (1)$$

SAMPLE AND PROCEDURE

The study focused on Palestinian customers in the West Bank who make purchases through online local channels. A stratified random sampling was employed to ensure representation across this demographic. The minimum sample size of 384 responses was determined based on the standards for achieving a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error and population proportion of 0.5, following the guidelines set by (Ahmad and Halim, 2017). This calculation was guided by the formula used in prior research, such as (Murrar *et al.*, 2021a).

Here, 'z' represents the z-score, 'e' signifies the margin of error, 'N' denotes the population size, and 'p' represents the population proportion. A total of 760 participants were communicated, with their email addresses sourced from various commercial institutions. These participants were sent email invitations that included a link to the online questionnaire, hosted on Google's platform. The distribution of these surveys was strategically aligned with the geographic distribution of the population across Palestinian regions as suggested by Murrar *et al.* (2021b), Murrar *et al.*, (2024). The breakdown of respondents was as follows: 44% from the northern region, 31% from the middle region, and 25% from the southern region. The email invitations clearly stated the purpose of the study and emphasized that participation was voluntary, with an assurance of complete confidentiality for all responses. Approximately two weeks after the initial distribution, a follow-up reminder email was sent to maximize the response rate. Ultimately, a total of 410 valid questionnaires were collected, achieving a response rate of 54%.

TECHNICAL METHOD

This research selected Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) as the most suitable technique for examining the relationships among multiple dependent variables (Streiner, 2005). SEM offers the advantage of simultaneously conducting multiple regressions and providing a comprehensive assessment of model fit, making it well-suited for analyzing complex models.

SEM with maximum likelihood relies on several statistical measures, including the chi-square statistic and various indices, to evaluate the goodness of fit. These indices include the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (RMR), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Relative Fit Index (RFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), and Tucker Lewis Index (TLI) (Diamantopoulos *et al.*, 2000).

Moreover, this research incorporates Bayesian SEM, which allows for the integration of prior information into the analysis, providing an alternative estimation method to the maximum likelihood approach. By comparing the outcomes derived from both maximum likelihood and Bayesian SEM, the study aims to verify the robustness of the findings across different estimation techniques and to confirm the consistency of the relationships observed between the customer satisfaction and repurchase intention.

VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY

The content validity of the questionnaire was ensured through an extensive literature review. The survey measured two primary constructs: customer satisfaction and repurchase intention within the local retail channel. These constructs were chosen based on their relevance to the research objectives and their widely acknowledged importance in marketing research. Customer satisfaction construct was assessed using items adapted from the Customer Satisfaction Index (CSI) model, which is well-documented in literature (Vasić *et al.*, 2019). The survey included 4 items to gauge various aspects of satisfaction. The original scale was modified to better fit the context of local retail channels, particularly in the digital environment. Repurchase intention were adapted from the scale developed by Lin and Lekhawipat (2014). Modifications were made to reflect specific online shopping behaviors and intentions in a localized retail setting. The construct was measured using 3 items that asked participants about their likelihood to return, recommend the site to others, and their anticipated frequency of future purchases.

Furthermore, to assess the instrument's internal consistency, Cronbach's alpha was employed. This widely used measure of scale reliability is considered satisfactory when it reaches a value of 0.70 or higher, signifying strong internal consistency among the items within the same construct (Gliem and Gliem, 2003). The results of our primary sample showed that Cronbach's alpha (α) was 0.820. This result indicates that the instrument maintains a high internal consistency and reliability level, further enhancing the credibility of the research findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In evaluating the overall model fit, the results in the AMOS output showed that the Chi-square for goodness-of-fit is 4.65, with 2 degrees of freedom. The value of Chi-square divided by degrees of freedom, a goodness of fit measure, is a better fit when it is less than 5 or $P > 0.05$. (Diamantopoulos *et al.*, 2000). In this research, the value of Chi-square divided by degrees of freedom is 4.65, and $P = 0.098$, indicating that the model is a good fit.

According to Diamantopoulos *et al.* (2000), a good fit of the model is indicated by a goodness of fit index (GFI) value exceeding 0.90. In this research, the GFI value of 0.998 confirms the goodness of fit. Additionally, well-fitting models have values less than 0.05 for the RMR. In this research, the RMR value of 0.005 indicates a good fit. The RMSEA measures the model's fit to the population covariance matrix and is considered acceptable with a value less than 0.08 and ideally less than 0.05. The RMSEA value in this research is 0.043, which falls within the ideal range. Furthermore, values close to 1 for the CFI, NFI, RFI, AGFI, and TLI suggest a good fit. In this research, the values of NFI (0.999), RFI (0.998), AGFI (0.971), TLI (0.987), and CFI (0.999) indicate a good fit for the estimated model.

The Adjusted R^2 is the percentage that explains the variation of the predictor constructs (Streiner, 2005). A higher R-squared value indicates a better fit of the model to the data. According to Chin (1998), an R-squared value of 33 to 67% is considered moderate, while a value of 67-75% is considered moderate-strong. In this research, the predictors of customer satisfaction have a moderate explanatory power, accounting for 62% of the variation in customer satisfaction. Meanwhile, the predictors of repurchase intention showed moderate-strong explanatory power, accounting for 74% of the variation in the repurchase intention.

In the Bayesian SEM conducted for this research, the posterior predictive p-value (PPP) is a Bayesian measure used to compare the observed data with data simulated from the model based on the estimated parameters. A PPP value near 0.5 generally signals a good model fit, indicating that the observed data are likely under the proposed model. The PPP value found in this study is precisely 0.41, which suggests that the model's predictions are in harmony with the observed data.

DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

The analysis involved calculating mean scores for the six customer satisfaction drivers. Among these drivers, the time-saving factor displayed the highest mean score, with a value of 3.44. It was closely followed by the information availability and delivery service factors, which had mean scores of 3.40 and 3.28, respectively. However, the perceived price, perceived quality, and customer support factors received lower mean scores, with values of 2.82, 2.75, and 2.44, respectively. Notably, the mean values for overall customer satisfaction (3.36) and repurchase intention (3.28) were similar.

The findings revealed that, in general, Palestinian customers who engage with online local retailers tend to express satisfaction. Specifically, 54% of these customers reported being satisfied, 8% expressed dissatisfaction, and 38% remained neutral in their responses. While examining the product categories, clothing emerged as the most popular product type, accounting for 40% of purchases made online through local sales channels. On the other end of the range, the food and grocery products category had the lowest share, representing only 6% of the total. Intermediately, personal accessories constituted 22%, electrical and electronic tools stood at 17%, and home appliances comprised 15%. Interestingly, customers who purchased electrical and electronic tools had the highest satisfaction levels, while the food and grocery products category had the lowest proportion of satisfied customers.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND ITS DIMENSIONS

Table 1 presents the impact of individual predictors on customer satisfaction. All the predictors listed in Table 1 exhibit significant and positive effects on the customer satisfaction variable, with their respective statistical significance values at $p < .05$. Consequently, this support from the data confirms all the hypotheses set forth in the literature review. These hypotheses suggested that factors such as product information, product quality, price, time-saving, customer support, and delivery service significantly enhance customer satisfaction when shopping online from local retailers. These findings both validate the theoretical framework proposed and align with previous research conducted by Vasić *et al.* (2019), Choi *et al.*, (2019), Brand *et al.*, (2020), Zhong and Moon, (2020).

TABLE 1: STANDARDIZED REGRESSION WEIGHTS OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION

Relationship	Estimate	S.E.	P	Result
Customer Satisfaction <--- Customer Support	0.162	0.033	0.000	Significant
Customer Satisfaction <--- Information Availability	0.283	0.037	0.000	Significant
Customer Satisfaction <--- Perceived Quality	0.144	0.030	0.000	Significant
Customer Satisfaction <--- Perceived Price	0.199	0.031	0.000	Significant
Customer Satisfaction <--- Delivery Service	0.178	0.022	0.000	Significant
Customer Satisfaction <--- Time-Saving	0.118	0.023	0.000	Significant

The results showed the significant influence of information availability on customer satisfaction, indicated by the highest estimate among the variables in this model at 0.283, with a p-value of less than 0.05. This demonstrates that information availability is a critical factor in enhancing customer satisfaction. Specifically, information related to price and product serves as a powerful tool for attracting new customers. The result indicated that customers tend to express dissatisfaction when retailers post product images on platforms like Facebook or Instagram without accompanying price information, requiring interested customers to send text messages to inquire about the product's price. In such cases, customers may decide not to purchase or do so with unrealistic expectations. Given that customers expect the product to align with the online-posted information, incomplete or inaccurate details can lead to product returns or a decision not to make future purchases. These findings are in harmony with prior research, which has consistently emphasized that accurate, reliable, updated, and easily accessible information plays a pivotal role in shaping customer satisfaction and raising realistic expectations (Pham and Ahammad, 2017, Tandon *et al.*, 2018, Sreeram *et al.*, 2017, Bonny, 2019, Vasić *et al.*, 2019).

Customer satisfaction also depends on the alignment of product quality and price with the expectations that customers have formed based on the information provided by the retailer. Patterson (1993) emphasizes that product quality is the most fundamental determinant of customer satisfaction. Products are marketed with specific specifications and quality levels that are appropriate for their prices. The study indicated that customer dissatisfaction becomes evident when retailers deliver products with undesirable characteristics, such as the wrong color, diminished specifications, lower manufacturing quality, or additional charges for service delivery. The significance of quality and price as predictors of customer satisfaction has widespread support in the existing literature (Jiang and Rosenbloom, 2005, Suhartanto *et al.*, 2019, Rahman and Yu, 2019, Zhong and Moon, 2020, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Brand *et al.*, 2020, Alalwan, 2020).

The result revealed that time-saving, delivery service, and customer support exert a significant and positive influence on customer satisfaction, aligning with the findings of previous studies (Uzir *et al.* 2021, Vasić *et al.*, 2019, Cha and Shin, 2021). Consequently, local consumers mainly seek online products at competitive prices while prioritizing savings in time, effort, and expenses that would otherwise be incurred by physically accessing the local market. However, it is essential to acknowledge that time saving may not be the primary concern for specific households, as they derive enjoyment and social interaction from traditional face-to-face shopping experiences. Furthermore, the results indicated that late deliveries and additional delivery charges contribute to customer dissatisfaction with the delivery service.

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND REPURCHASE INTENTION

Customers' satisfaction levels increase when they have positive and fulfilling experiences with a retailer. This satisfaction becomes a driving force behind their intention to repurchase from the same retailer. Satisfied customers are more likely to return for future purchases. This research empirically measured this relationship as shown by Table 2, where customer satisfaction is an exogenous variable and the repurchase intention within the online sales channel is an endogenous variable. The results showed that customer satisfaction significantly affects the repurchase intention where $\beta=0.667$ and $p=.001$. This finding supports the hypothesis suggested in the literature that customer satisfaction has a positive and significant impact on repurchase intention, supporting studies of (Choi et al., 2019, Hult et al., 2019, Tandon et al., 2020, Dai and Lee, 2018).

TABLE 2: STANDARDIZED REGRESSION WEIGHTS OF REPURCHASE INTENTION

Relationship	Estimate	S.E.	P	Result
Customer Satisfaction <---Repurchase Intention	0.667	0.029	0.000	Significant
Repurchase Intention <--- Customer Support	0.085	0.026	0.001	Significant
Repurchase Intention <--- Information Availability	0.072	0.03	0.017	Significant
Repurchase Intention <--- Perceived Quality	0.088	0.024	0.000	Significant
Repurchase Intention <--- Delivery Service	0.049	0.018	0.006	Significant

The study showed that information availability positively impacts repurchase intention, where $P=0.001$. This finding supports the hypothesis suggested in the literature that information availability has a positive and significant impact on repurchase intention (Miao et al., 2022). When customers perceive that the online retailer provides reliable product information, they are more likely to develop an intention to repurchase. Additionally, information availability indirectly affects repurchase intention by enhancing customer satisfaction. Satisfied customers, driven by the accessibility of quality information, are more motivated to engage in repeat purchases within the online local retail channel.

Furthermore, the study revealed that perceived quality significantly impacts repurchase intention, where $P=0.017$. This result confirms the hypothesis found in the literature that there is a positive and significant relationship between perceived quality and repurchase intention (Izzudin and Novandari, 2018). Customers arrive with certain quality expectations when ordering products online, primarily based on the information provided by the retailer. Customer satisfaction is achieved when the delivered products align with or exceed these quality expectations, leading to a higher likelihood of repurchase intention.

Furthermore, the results indicated that the delivery service positively impacts repurchase intention, where $P=0.006$. This result validates the hypothesis presented in the literature that there is a positive and significant relationship between delivery service and repurchase intention (Uzir et al., 2021, Vasić et al., 2019, Cha and Shin, 2021, Roy Dholakia and Zhao, 2010). Online shoppers highly value timely, reliable, and convenient delivery services. When customers receive their orders promptly and in good condition, it positively influences their satisfaction with the retailer. Satisfied customers are more motivated to return for future purchases.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD AND BAYESIAN ESTIMATION RESULTS

Table 3 presents a comparison between Maximum Likelihood (ML) and Bayesian estimation techniques applied in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to understand the intricacies of customer satisfaction and repurchase intention dynamics. This comparative analysis helped to identify any divergences or confirmations between the different methodologies, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the research findings.

TABLE 3: ESTIMATED PARAMETERS OF SEM USING ML AND BAYESIAN ESTIMATION

Relationship	ML- SEM	B- SEM
Customer Satisfaction <---Customer Support	0.162	0.161
Customer Satisfaction <--- Information Availability	0.283	0.283
Customer Satisfaction <--- Perceived Quality	0.144	0.146
Customer Satisfaction <--- Perceived Price	0.199	0.198
Customer Satisfaction <--- Delivery Service	0.178	0.18
Customer Satisfaction <--- Time-Saving	0.118	0.118
Repurchase Intention <--- Customer Support	0.162	0.085
Customer Satisfaction <---Repurchase Intention	0.667	0.667
Repurchase Intention <--- Information Availability	0.085	0.073
Repurchase Intention <--- Perceived Quality	0.072	0.087
Repurchase Intention <--- Delivery Service	0.088	0.049

Table 3 shows that the relationships influencing customer satisfaction exhibit strong consistency between the two models. Factors such as Customer Support, Information Availability, Perceived Quality, Perceived Price, Delivery Service, and Time-Saving all showed similar impacts on customer satisfaction, with almost identical estimates across both ML and Bayesian methods. For example, Information Availability consistently showed a significant impact on customer satisfaction with an estimate of 0.283 in both models, underscoring its pivotal role in determining customer satisfaction levels.

However, the analysis also reveals some differences in how certain factors influence repurchase intention across the two SEM approaches. While the relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Repurchase Intention remained stable and strong across both methods, with an identical estimate of 0.667, other factors such as Customer Support and Delivery Service showed discrepancies. For instance, the impact of Customer Support on Repurchase Intention was 0.162 in ML-SEM and decreased to 0.085 in B-SEM. Similarly, Delivery Service's impact on Repurchase Intention differed between the two methods (0.088 in ML-SEM versus 0.049 in B-SEM). These differences suggest that the estimation method may influence the sensitivity of the model to certain variables, particularly those affecting repurchase intention.

Overall, the comparative analysis between ML-SEM and Bayesian SEM in Table 3 not only strengthens the validity of the SEM model used but also highlights the reliability of Bayesian SEM in providing consistent results with traditional ML approaches. The few observed discrepancies in predicting repurchase intention emphasize the importance of considering multiple estimation methods to fully capture the model dynamics. This detailed examination is essential for researchers and practitioners seeking to utilize these findings in strategic decision-making, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the factors that drive customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions in retail settings.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research investigated the dynamics of customer satisfaction and repurchase intention in the online local retail channel through a comprehensive analysis of various factors such as Information Availability, Perceived Quality, Perceived Price, Customer Support, Time Saving, and Delivery Service. This study has provided valuable mechanisms that drive customer behavior in the digital local retail landscape.

Primary data through questionnaire responses were collected from 410 Palestinian customers. Cronbach's alpha was conducted to measure the internal consistency. Structural equation modeling was utilized to evaluate the causal diagram by examining the relationships among the constructs while using the AMOS software package.

The results indicated that information availability, perceived quality, perceived price, customer support, time-saving, and delivery service positively impact customer satisfaction and indirectly influence repurchase intention from local online retail channels. In the online local retail channel context, these findings collectively emphasize that retailers must use these factors to enhance customer satisfaction and stimulate repurchase intention. This research contributes valuable insights to academia and practitioners, stressing the need for a customer-centric approach to thrive in the digital retail landscape.

THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATIONS

This research makes significant theoretical contributions to online local retail by exploring the dynamics of customer satisfaction and repurchase intention within this digital landscape. The study employed structural equation modeling (SEM) techniques to assess causal relationships among the identified constructs. This methodological approach enables a deeper comprehension of how direct and indirect predictors influence customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions. By explaining these causal pathways, the study refines existing theoretical models, offering an understanding of customer dynamics in online local retail.

The findings of this research provide valuable practical implications for online local retailers seeking to enhance customer satisfaction and stimulate repurchase intentions. In today's competitive digital landscape, these insights can play a pivotal role in shaping a retailer's success.

Firstly, retailers should prioritize providing customers with comprehensive, accurate, and up-to-date product information online. This information includes detailed product descriptions, transparent pricing, and specifications. Retailers can significantly impact their satisfaction levels and encourage repeat purchases by ensuring customers can access this vital information easily.

Secondly, perceived quality emerges as a crucial factor. Retailers must ensure that the products' quality aligns with customer expectations. Consistency between online product descriptions and the actual delivered items is vital. When customers receive products that meet or exceed their perceived quality, their satisfaction levels rise, paving the way for future repurchases.

Competitive pricing also plays a critical role. Retailers must strike a balance between offering competitive prices and maintaining product quality. Fair and competitive pricing strategies that align with product value can positively influence customer satisfaction and, in turn, motivate repurchase intentions.

Responsive customer support is another key to success. Retailers should be prepared to address customer inquiries, concerns, and issues promptly and effectively. An efficient customer support system builds trust and reliability, ultimately increasing satisfaction and the likelihood of customers returning for more purchases.

Efficient delivery services such as timely, reliable, and convenient delivery processes are vital in online retail. Retailers must prioritize efficient shipping and delivery methods to ensure customers receive their orders as promised and in excellent condition. Finally, these practical implications underscore the pivotal role of customer satisfaction in online local retail. Retailers must prioritize customer-centric strategies that align with these findings to encourage positive shopping experiences and secure long-term success in the competitive digital market.

APPENDIX 1

Construct	Code	Item	Source
Information Availability	IA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that online product information provided by the retailer is identical to the information about the product in the offline channel (physical store)? To what extent do you agree or disagree that online product information is precise? To what extent do you agree or disagree that online product information is up to date? 	(Vasić et al., 2019)
Perceived Quality	P.Q.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that the quality of the product you ordered online is the same as that of the product purchased through the offline channel (physical store)? To what extent do you agree or disagree that online shopping provides the same purchasing terms and conditions as offline shopping? To what extent do you agree or disagree that the product ordered through the online channel is rarely incompatible with the product purchased through the offline channel? 	(Patterson, 1993, Chen and Dubinsky, 2003, Vasić et al., 2019)
Perceived Price	P.P.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that online shopping saves money compared to offline shopping? To what extent do you agree or disagree that online shopping is cheaper than offline shopping? To what extent do you agree or disagree that online shopping significantly reduces expenses per transaction compared to offline shopping? 	(Jiang and Rosenbloom, 2005, Vasić et al., 2019)
Time-Saving	T.S.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that online shopping saves time? To what extent do you agree or disagree that online shopping offers the possibility of shopping 24/7? To what extent do you agree or disagree that online shopping is a smart way of spending time? 	(Vasić et al., 2019)
Delivery Service	D.S.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that the option of free shipping in the online channel increases the frequency of purchases? To what extent do you agree or disagree that customers feel concerned about receiving the wrong product in the online channel? To what extent do you agree or disagree that the retailer offers delivery options in the online channel on weekends? 	(Patterson, 1993, Rudansky-Kloppers, 2014)
Customer Support	CT	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that the customer support provided by local online retailers accurately handles your inquiries and concerns? To what extent do you agree or disagree that local online retailers' customer support system calls you on time? To what extent do you agree or disagree that the customer support of local online retailers rapidly retrieves the information you requested? 	(Jun et al., 2004)
Customer Satisfaction	C.S.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that online local shopping makes the purchasing process interesting? To what extent do you agree or disagree that you would recommend online local shopping to other consumers? To what extent do you agree or disagree that you enjoy online local shopping? To what extent do you agree or disagree that you are satisfied that local retailers offer online options? To what extent do you agree or disagree that it is your opinion that online local shopping is excellent? 	(Ahn et al., 2004, Guo et al., 2012, Vasić et al., 2019, Choi et al., 2019)
Repurchase Intention	RI	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent do you agree or disagree that you anticipate repurchasing from shopping with the same online local retailer? To what extent do you agree or disagree that you will likely repurchase from the same online local retailer? To what extent do you agree or disagree that you expect repurchasing from the same online local retailer? 	(Lin and Lekhawipat, 2014)

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